

A STUDY OF THE FACTORS WHICH FASCINATE STUDENTS TOWARDS AN IDEAL VIRTUAL LEARNING PROGRAMME IN VASAI REGION DURING LOCKDOWN

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Abstract

In Covid-19 pandemic, due to nationwide lockdown every activity other than medical field has been frozen. Education sector had also gone through the stagnate position, where teachers and students cannot move from their residence, not able to gather at educational institute. Teacher's not able to connect with their learners in offline mode and so imparting of education had stopped. In this crisis period for delivering knowledge with maintaining social distance was an opportunity to explore virtual resources for imparting education. Education was started online. Teachers and students connected through various Apps and websites and continued the journey of teaching and learning. The research question is what are the factors which fascinate students towards virtual learning? It is dealt with from the assessment of the students from Vasai region. The methodology of the study is descriptive and empirical. The research study has been conducted by taking primary data collection with the help of structured questionnaire. In order to undertake the required study, 250 respondents from students were chosen from Vasai region as respondents. Statistical analysis of data calculation has been presented through Mean, Median, First Quartile and Cumulative percentage. It is concluded that the students are responsive to move towards virtual learning is depend upon the factors of their point of attraction.

Key Words: Covid-19, pandemic, social distance, virtual learning, Teacher, Students.

I. Introduction

पुस्तकस्था तु या विद्या परहस्तगतं धनम् ।

कार्यकाले समुत्पन्ने न सा विद्या न तद्धनम् ॥

“The knowledge which is residing in the book and one's wealth which is in possession of some other person is of no use at all. At the time of its need they will not be of any help for the person.”

This is what the situation in Covid-19 pandemic, due to lockdown in nationwide every activity other than medical field has been freeze. Education sector has also going through the stagnate position, where teachers and students cannot move from their residence, not able to gather at educational institute. Teacher's knowledge has retained with them and useless for students without carry forwarding. This is the crisis period for delivering knowledge with maintaining social distance; this could be the opportunity to explore virtual resources for imparting education. Prevention from COVID-19 is only possible through social distancing, which affect traditional educating system. Virtual teaching and learning has been able to bridge the gap which is created due to social distancing. This study has been carried out from the Vasai Region, which can be described as urban as well as rural region. Researcher tries to cognize what are the factors

which fascinate students towards virtual learning? Intention of the study was to analyze the factors which fascinate students towards virtual learning in Vasai Region.

II. Literature Review

(Alwin, July 2020) **The authors have analysed the perception of teachers towards online education system. They concluded that the willingness of the teacher to adopt to online teaching is important for the success of online education.**

(Charles Hodges, 2020), According to the researchers Covid-19 has brought about development of new skills among all stakeholders of education. After the pandemic is over proper evaluation should be done by all stakeholders about the Emergency Remote Teaching (ERT) used to be ready for future needs and disasters.

(Yurdugül, 2019) The study analyses the factors that affect learner's mode of teaching and learning in online environment. It concluded that self-efficacy, e-learning motivation and task value has a correlation with the mode of teaching and learning. The students with high task value, self learning motivation and self efficacy prefer blended learning. Out of the sample size of 64 respondents, 29 preferred blended learning and 35 preferred online learning. Only face to face learning was not preferred by the learners

(Bulut, 2007) The authors recommend that proper orientation of the students joining the online course will enable the student to have better understanding of the requirements and adaptation needed in the learning environment. More so focus should be on self regulation and student centered methods.

III. Objective Of The Study

1. To understand the virtual learning system.
2. To study the factors that fascinates students towards virtual learning.
3. To analyse the factors, that fascinate students towards virtual learning in Vasai Region.

IV. Hypotheses

Null Hypothesis (H₀):

H₀: "There are no significant factors fascinating students in an ideal virtual learning mode among learners in Vasai Region due to Covid-19 pandemic"

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁):

H₁: "There are significant factors fascinating students in an ideal virtual learning mode among learners in Vasai Region due to Covid-19 pandemic"

V. Research Methodology

The methodology of the study is descriptive and empirical. The study has been carried out by taking primary data collection. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. For the purpose of collecting data researcher has prepared questionnaire for the Study. In order to accomplish the required hypothesis of the study, 250 respondents from Under Graduate students were chosen from Vasai region as sample for the study. Statistical analysis of data calculation has been presented through Mean, Median, First Quartile and Cumulative percentage.

VI. Significance Of Study:

1. The study is fundamentally done to understand the factors on an ideal virtual learning due to Covid-19 pandemic.

2. It is an attempt to recognize the Conversions taken place in the learning process due to social distancing forced by Covid -19 pandemic.

VII. Analysis Of Data:

Table 01: Factors for Student's attraction towards online learning.

Research Question: What are the factors, which an Ideal online course should have to attract students .?						
Hypothesis: Students do not have any attraction towards online learning.						
Sr. No.	Factors considered by students to enroll in online course	Mean	Median	First Quartile	% Cumulative of 4 & 5	Ranking of the factors
1	Better Quality	3.79	4	3	63	1
2	Flexible Time period for completion	3.82	4	3	62	2
3	Easy to Understand E-content	3.7	4	3	60	3
4	Expert Faculty	3.78	4	3	60	4
5	Low fees	3.69	4	3	57	5
6	Fair Assessment Policy	3.56	4	3	54	6
7	Interaction	3.59	4	3	52	7
8	Credibility	3.65	4	3	50	8
9	Effective Curriculum	3.52	4	3	48	9

Table 1: Grading Table¹

Grading of Response	Mean	Median	Mode	First Quartile	Cumulative Score of Strongly Agree and Agree.
High level of attractiveness towards the factor	3.6 and Above	4&5	4&5	4&5	80% and above
Medium Preference	2.6 to 3.6	3	3	3	60% to 80%
Low Preference	Less than 2.6	1&2	1%2	1&2	Less than 60%

¹ Ahlam Alghamdia, A. C. (August 2019)

Interpretation and Findings

The mean score of above 3.6 shows high level of attractiveness of learners towards all factors of online courses. The median score of 4 of all factors also show high level of attractiveness of learners towards all factors of online courses. The first quartile score of all the factors are in the range of 3 showing medium preference towards factors attracting students to online course. The first 4 out of 9 factors are in the range of 60% to 80% showing medium preference and the remaining 5 factors are in less than 60% range showing low preference for factors attracting online courses.

So we can conclude that the learners are showing a low to medium preference towards factors attracting online courses.

Hypothesis testing

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
0.921	0.922	9

Cronbachs Alpha of 0.922 means high reliability of data and further statistical analysis can be conducted. **All the Cronbach Alpha are greater than 0.75 showing high reliability of the factors. Even if some items are deleted still the Cronbach Alpha remains above 0.75 showing high reliability of the factors.**

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
Between People		1371.252	207	6.624		
Within People	Between Items	19.257	8	2.407	4.587	.000
	Residual	868.965	1656	.525		
	Total	888.222	1664	.534		
Total		2259.474	1871	1.208		
Grand Mean = 3.6768						

The p value <0.05 and so the hypothesis that the factors don't effect choice of online courses is failed to be accepted. It is concluded that learners are affected by all the factors towards online courses.

VIII. Limitations Of The Study

In spite of all sincere hard work, in order to assemble significant information and data, there are some limitations such as:

1. The latitude of the present study is restricted to Vasai region.
2. The questionnaire respondents were mostly College students in under graduate (UG) level.
3. Chances of biased reply from the respondents.

IX. CONCLUSION:

Social distancing forced by Covid -19 pandemic may create hurdle for education, but the dedicated teachers and students can overcome this situation with the help of virtual teaching and learning. Sooner or later the modern education will be in the form of digital education or online/ app base education. A pandemic is an opportunity to grab the future education system in present only. Learners prefer better quality of course content something which enables them to upgrade their skills. They prefer flexible time duration to complete the course. The content should be easily

understandable and use expert faculty to deliver the content. The cost structure of the course should be affordable. There should be fair assessment policy for the courses. The preferences of the learners listed in the table were agreed upon by more than 50% of the respondents in the survey.

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